

IMPACT OF GLOBALIZATION ON TOURISMSTUDY ON SUSTAINING TOURISM
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Introduction:

Tourism is a well-known term used by many on a regular basis. It is one of the fast-growing industries of today. Due to industrialization and progress in science and technology, people have started travelling from one to another away from their city of residence or work.

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There has been a lot of development in the tourism industry. Earlier men used to travel to hunt for food. This was the first visible experience of men travelling from one place to another and finding out new places. Then with the discovery of wheels people started travelling by carts.

In the beginning the railways were the main source for connecting many cities and town which were useful to carry food, raw materials and also helped many people to reach from one place to another. Then steamships were introduced which carried many people from one country to another via waterways. This gave a boost to international travelers who were able to travel many places for education, work, tourism etc.

The faster growth and expansion of foreign tourism is the result of augmentation in leisure, peace, higher standard of living, advancement in transport, easier communication, visibility of new patterns in world tourism, increase in the number of travel companies, studying new languages etc.

Dimensions Of Travel And Tourism
Historical Dimension-

During the Paleolithic Age many regions were explored by the man. This in turn also increased the activity of travelling.

During the Neolithic Age new dimension were seen in the field of travel and tourism. The invention of wheels changed the concept of travelling on roads. With the invention of coins, there was an increase in trade and business. Hence many businessmen started travelling from one place to another for the purpose of trade. This era can be said to be the turning point towards the beginning of the modern era in the field of travel and tourism.

Trade and commerce had become very common during the middle ages. This became the main source of travel for man. He started taking long tours to faraway lands. This was possible because of improvement in the infrastructure like better roads, availability of small houses or huts to stay etc.

The nineteenth century marked the beginning of modern age of tourism. With the development and progress of industries, there was a drastic change in the travelling pattern. There was discovery of railways and waterways which made travel easier for men. Factories were set up in big towns. The burden of man increased and he started to take break from work. This can be marked as the beginning of tourism for leisure.

Economic Dimension-

Travel and tourism have a significant impact on the economy of any country. Many countries in the world are

dependent on tourism as a means of their livelihood. It creates employment opportunities in various sectors like hotel industry, transportation, lodging and boarding etc. The people who visit different countries other than their place or residence or work tend to create income for the public and private sector of that country. This in turn can raise the GDP of the country. This is mostly beneficial to the developing countries for its growth as a strong economy can change the overall look of any nation. The income received from tourism can be sometimes even more than the one that is received from industries (specially the countries having a low industrial base).

It is seen that many countries expand tourism as it impacts the economy in a positive way. However there has also been a negative impact on tourism due to the ongoing pandemic. But such situations do not usually arise.

The monetary advantages in the sector are gigantic resulting in the improvement of infrastructure, building of new tourist attractions and other facilities. In order to attract more and more foreign and local tourists a large amount of money is spent on this sector. People from developed countries are more attracted towards the nature and beauty in the developing nations. The geographical factors of a country also play a vital role in the development of tourism.

The tourism industry has always helped the developing nations in many ways. The steady growth that is visible in this sector helps these nations to gain a huge portion of international tourist markets. The most important economic advantages are in terms of foreign exchange (Forex). The sum granted in foreign currency per tourist is varied from one tourist destination to another as the value of different currency is different. The income received from the foreign tourists in forex earnings is beneficial to the income of the nation as it increases the foreign currency reserve for the state.

The income from foreign tourism may not always yield profit as sometimes there are disbursements involved which need to be set against it. The developing countries also get various opportunities of receiving foreign exchange by delivering the necessary goods and services to meet the tourist's needs.

Thus, it can be concluded that the tourism industry not only gives pleasure and happiness to the wanderlusts but also gives equal opportunities to the ones who are in need of employment.¹

Psychological Dimension-

If anyone asks you a reason for why are you going for holiday or if you ask your friend the same question, you might find varying answers. Thus, the purpose of taking a holiday may differ from person to person.

A) Physical motivation

It is related to bodily relaxation, specific medical treatment, sports activities etc. it is connected with one's physical health and well-being.

B) Cultural motivation

It is related with one's pleasure of traveling to learn and understand about the cultural, art, heritage, music, folk-art etc.

C) Status and prestige motivation

It is related to the needs of personal benefit and development. It can be to fulfill various interests like professional, education, hobbies etc.

D) Interpersonal motivation

It can be termed as the desire to meet or visit their relatives, friends, family etc. or to go away from the daily routine for a small refreshing break.

Impact Of Global Pandemic On Tourism

The global pandemic has affected all the fields and now with the reopening of places, many sectors are becoming stable again.

The pandemic has had a great impact on travel and tourism which is mostly negative in nature. Following are some of the impacts of global pandemic on travel and tourism industry:-

Negative Impact

A) Closing borders:

The international borders were closed since the announcement of the lockdown in march 2020. With its closure, many international travel destinations were sealed which restricted the travelers. The economy was greatly affected as the foreign income was at a standstill. Closing of airports, stopping of flights were some of the effects of this pandemic.

B) Hospitality sector:

Hospitality plays a vital role in the tourism industry. A hotel, lodge, restaurant etc. is usually remembered for the hospitality services it provides. The work related to this is sector is generally ground work. As the whole world was in the lockdown, the hospitality sector was largely affected. It is without doubt that the hospitality sector has witnessed a major loss during this pandemic.

C) Employment:

As a result of the pandemic, millions of the people related to tourism sector have lost their jobs. This is not only visible in our country but has affected the world at large. As transportation had restrictions, the common man faced difficulties to travel from his house to his work place. Freshers who wish to start a career in this sector are facing issues at the beginning of their journey.

D) Impact on transportation:

Transportation includes roadways, railways, waterways and airways. The global pandemic had closed the international as well as national borders. Restrictions were imposed on transportation making it difficult to travel. The railway stations, airports, bus stations etc. were open for only necessary and emergency services. The norm of social distancing has also affected the railways as they are the most crowded means of transportation who carry loads of people daily. The airlines were also impacted and some of them on were on the verge of closing.

E) Decline of international travelers:

Airways are the most preferred mode of transportation to reach the foreign land. To avoid the spread of virus across nations, the airways were shut down making it impossible to reach the desired destination.

F) Economy:

Tremendous decline was visible in the economies of the world. Many countries that are dependent on tourism have suffered huge losses. It is one of the largest sectors that imports and exports in order to fulfill the demands of the tourists. Many lost their jobs which in turn affected the money flow in this sector.

Positive Impact

A) Environment:

Environment includes forests, trees, wildlife, oceans, rivers, seas, air etc. The pollution that is emitted from vehicles and industries effects the quality of air. Due to the lockdown, there were many positive improvements in

the nature around us. There was an improvement in the quality of air as there was less emission of carbon monoxide and carbon dioxide. The forests become greener and fresh. The emissions let out in the water bodies from the factories decreased which in turn improved the water quality of many rivers. Due the restricted movements noise pollution was also under control. The human activities that created noise like the use of machines, construction work etc. were reduced which in turn lessen the noise pollution. The ozone layer was healed at some level.

Due to decrease in tourism, the tourist stops were less polluted and the natural beauty flourished. The plastic pollution was reduced and other ecofriendly options were adopted. Festivals too were celebrated on a small scale reducing the pollution which affects the environment.

Thus, it can be said that many positive changes were seen in the environment and the people in general are becoming more and more aware.

B) Increase in domestic tourism:

The international borders were closed due to the global pandemic. With the unlock that started from June 2020 many sectors started working. The tourism industry also began its work but the cross-country transportation is still closed. Many tourists who wish to step out of the house started travelling in their own countries which flourished the regional tourism. New trends of staycation have also influenced the minds of the youth. Generally, the youths prefer to travel less and relax more. At such times, grand hotels and resorts offer best deals for staycation where one can relax as well as work from that place.

Conclusion:

The flow of tourism has always been with various ups and downs and globalization has played an important role in this since a past few decades. The sector of tourism and very complex in nature but are something that help in the growth and development of oneself as well as the nation.

The increase in demand seen in the past few years in the sector of tourism have impacted the nation in a positive way. New trends have emerged and are being followed at a global level making it a trending topic amongst the masses. The gap between the developing and developed nations is decreasing as many people from the developed nations are visiting the developing nations for leisure, work, education etc. until they reach their complete satisfaction.

Some of the suggestions would be:

- To formulate policies for tourism with a long-lasting approach, keeping in mind the domestic as well as international approach,
- To expand new tactics to increase the nation's potential in the tourism sector,
- To make policies for the progress domestic tourism and help them to reach at a global level
- To develop infrastructure to attract the tourism of other nations.

If some of the above-mentioned suggestions are taken into consideration, there can still be hope to cure some of the problems related to tour